

Non-Darcy MHD Mixed Convection of Fe₃O₄ Nanofluid in a Vertical Cylindrical Annulus with Viscous Dissipation and Arrhenius Activation Energy

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Abstract:

This study investigates the combined effects of viscous dissipation, Darcy and Forchheimer flow and Arrhenius activation energy on magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) mixed convective heat and mass transfer of Fe₃O₄ nanofluid confined within a vertical cylindrical annulus. The study considers three base fluids ethylene glycol, engine oil, and kerosene in the presence of a non-uniform internal heat source and a porous medium under non-Darcy (Forchheimer) resistance. The governing nonlinear coupled equations for momentum, energy, and nanoparticle concentration are defined using Buongiorno's nanofluid model and solved numerically via the finite element method with quadratic interpolation functions. The results demonstrate that magnetic field strength, viscous dissipation, Forchheimer inertia, and Prandtl number suppress axial velocity and species transport, while thermal radiation, nanoparticle volume fraction, thermo-diffusion, and activation energy significantly enhance thermal and solutal fields. Joule heating raises temperature but reduces velocity and concentration. Comparative analysis shows that ethylene glycol-based Fe₃O₄ nanofluid consistently exhibits superior velocity and heat transfer performance, whereas engine oil-based nanofluid produces higher nanoparticle concentration levels. Validation of the numerical scheme is gained through close agreement of skin friction, Nusselt number, and Sherwood number with existing literature for limiting Newtonian cases. A detailed comparison between inner and outer annular walls shows that inner-wall transport is shear-dominated, while outer-wall transport is mainly convection-driven. The results provide valuable insight into the design of annular MHD thermal systems involving reactive nanofluids and porous media.

Keywords: Variable viscosity, electrical conductivity, thermal radiation, ohmic dissipation, cylindrical annulus.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Non-Newtonian fluid mechanics is essential for modelling a wide range of industrial and natural processes, including polymer processing, suspensions, slurries, lubricants, biological fluids, and geological flows. Unlike Newtonian fluids, non-Newtonian fluids exhibit nonlinear stress-strain relationships, leading to higher-order governing equations and more complex boundary conditions. Early studies addressing such complexities include third-grade fluid flow between coaxial cylinders by Malik et al. [1], MHD non-Newtonian flow over stretching surfaces by Azeemshahzad and Ali [2], and variable-viscosity Oldroyd-type fluid flow in

annular geometries by Hussain et al. [3]. Casson and related non-Newtonian models have since been widely employed to describe yield-stress and shear-thinning behavior under thermal and magnetic effects [4-6].

Enhancement of heat transfer performance has attracted increasing attention due to the low thermal conductivity of conventional heat transfer fluids such as water, ethylene glycol, and oils. The concept of nanofluids, introduced by Choi [7], involves dispersing nanoscale solid particles into base fluids to improve thermal transport properties. Subsequent studies demonstrated that nanofluids significantly alter convective heat transfer characteristics depending on nanoparticle volume fraction, base-fluid properties, and flow configuration. Investigations by Putra et al. [8], Wen and Ding [9], and Jou and Tzeng [10] highlighted the sensitivity of natural convection to nanoparticle concentration. Annular and enclosure-based nanofluid convection was further explored by Mokhtari-Moghari et al. [11], Parvin et al. [12], and Soleimani et al. [13].

Cylindrical annular geometries are widely encountered in heat exchangers, nuclear reactors, geothermal systems, and chemical processing equipment. Natural and mixed convection in annuli especially when filled with porous media has been extensively studied due to its practical relevance. Foundational investigations include Caltagirone [14], Prasad and Kulacki [15], and Jha [16], who examined buoyancy-driven convection in porous annular domains. At higher flow velocities, inertial effects become important, requiring the adoption of non-Darcy (Darcy Forchheimer) models. The influence of non-Darcy resistance on annular convection was reported by Shivakumara et al. [17], Mallikarjuna et al. [18], and Alivene et al. [19].

The incorporation of magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) effects provides an effective mechanism for controlling flow and heat transfer in electrically conducting fluids. The application of a magnetic field introduces Lorentz forces that suppress fluid motion while influencing thermal transport through Joule heating. Significant contributions to MHD non-Newtonian and nanofluid flow analysis have been reported by Nadeem [20], Khalid et al. [21], Raju et al. [22], and Madhusudhana Reddy et al. [23], emphasizing the coupled roles of magnetic field strength, viscous dissipation, and thermal diffusion.

Among various nanoparticles, magnetite (Fe_3O_4) nanoparticles are particularly attractive due to their strong magnetic properties, electrical conductivity, chemical stability, and biomedical relevance. Chamkha et al. [24] conducted analytical and numerical investigations of Fe_3O_4 -based nanofluid flow, while Majeed et al. [25] examined heat transfer characteristics of Fe_3O_4 nanofluids in different base fluids. More recently, Shamshuddin et al. [26] analyzed convective transport of ethylene glycol based magnetic nanofluids in porous cylindrical annuli with variable viscosity, demonstrating enhanced thermal performance.

Chemical reaction effects and activation energy play a crucial role in heat and mass transfer processes involving reactive nanofluids. Activation energy, commonly modeled using the Arrhenius law, governs reaction rates, species diffusion, and non-equilibrium transport behavior. Several studies have shown that activation energy significantly influences concentration distribution, thermal boundary layers, and mass transfer rates in nanofluid and MHD systems [27]. Its inclusion provides a more realistic description of chemically reactive transport phenomena in energy and process engineering applications.

Despite the extensive literature on nanofluid convection, MHD effects, porous annular flows, and activation energy, studies that simultaneously account for Arrhenius activation energy, non-Darcy porous resistance, and Fe_3O_4 nanofluids in a vertical cylindrical annulus remain scarce. Motivated by this research gap, the present study investigates MHD mixed convective heat and mass transfer of Fe_3O_4 nanofluid confined within a vertical porous cylindrical annulus, considering ethylene glycol, engine oil, and kerosene as base fluids. The coupled nonlinear governing equations are solved numerically using the finite element method, and the effects of

key physical parameters on velocity, temperature, concentration, skin friction, Nusselt number, and Sherwood number are systematically examined.

Novelties of the Present Study

- Studying the non-Newtonian behavior of Casson particles mixed with magnetic Fe_3O_4 –Eg/Eo/Kr nanoparticles in cylinders that are stacked on top of each other, a shape that is useful for real devices.
- Adding Arrhenius activation energy, which connects the effects of heat movement on chemical reactions.
- An analysis of the differences between base fluids, focusing on how they affect speed, temperature, and transport properties.
- Providing numerical standards that can be used to build and improve MHD flow and annular heat transfer systems.

Real-Time Applications

- High-performance cooling of electronics, reactors, and heat exchanges using Fe_3O_4 -based Casson nanofluids to improve heat transfer is possible with advanced cooling systems.
- Energy systems: controlling heat in sun collectors, storing heat energy, and cooling loops in power plants.
- Controlling reactive flows in circular reactors with changing qualities and activation energy that affect reaction rates is a part of chemical and process engineering.
- Engineering for oil and gas: Nanofluids that don't follow the laws of physics flow in wellbores and annuli for drilling fluids and better oil recovery.
- Biomedical analogs: Modeling blood-like movements and magnetically controlled drug transport (Casson fluid relevance).
- High-speed or rapid heat transfer: This is when Cattaneo–Christov non-Fourier heat conduction gives more accurate temperature forecasts.

In this paper we discuss the effect of variable viscosity, electrical conductivity on non-Darcy MHD convective heat and mass transfer flow of thermally radiation Casson nanofluid Ethylene Glycol/Engine oil/Kerosene base Fe_3O_4 fluids incorporating Ohmic dissipation through a porous medium in co-axial cylindrical duct where the boundaries are maintained at uniform temperature and concentration T_w and C_w . The behaviour of velocity, temperature and concentration is analyzed by executing coupled equations numerically. The skin friction, the rate of heat and mass transfer on the cylinders has also been obtained for variations in the governing parameters.

2. Mathematical Formulation:

A mixed convection flow in a vertical circular annulus filled with a porous medium is considered, with both walls maintained at constant temperature and concentration. The velocity, temperature, and concentration fields are assumed to be fully developed, and all physical properties of the fluid and porous medium are taken to be constant. The flow is driven by a uniform axial pressure gradient together with thermal and solutal buoyancy forces, while density variations are restricted to the buoyancy terms through the Boussinesq approximation. The Brinkman–Forchheimer extended Darcy model is employed to represent the momentum transport in the porous region, accounting for viscous, inertial, and boundary effects. The resulting momentum, energy, and species diffusion equations are coupled, nonlinear, and describe a unidirectional axial flow within the cylindrical annulus.

$$-\frac{\partial p}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{\varepsilon r \rho_{nf}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\lambda_1}\right) \mu_{nf} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial w}{\partial r}\right) - \left(1 + \frac{1}{\lambda_1}\right) \left(\frac{\mu_{nf}}{k \rho_{nf}}\right) w - \left(\frac{\sigma_{nf} \mu_e^2 H_o^2}{\rho_{nf} r^2}\right) w \left| \right. \quad (1)$$

$$-\left(\frac{\varepsilon F}{\rho_{nf} \sqrt{k}}\right)(w^2) + (\rho\beta)_{nf} g(T - T_w) = 0$$

$$\left. \left(w \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} = \left(\frac{k_{nf}}{\rho C_p}\right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial T}{\partial r}\right) + \frac{q'''}{\rho C_p} - \frac{1}{r(\rho C_p)} \frac{\partial(rq_R)}{\partial r} + \left(1 + \frac{1}{\lambda_1}\right) \frac{\mu_{nf}}{\rho C_p} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial r}\right)^2 \right. \right. \quad (2)$$

$$\left. \left. + \frac{\sigma_{nf} \mu_e^2 H_o^2}{\rho C_p} (w^2) + \frac{Q_1}{\rho C_p} (C - C_w) + \left(\frac{\mu_{nf}}{k(\rho C_p)}\right)(w^2) + \left(\frac{\varepsilon \rho_{nf} F}{\rho C_p}\right)(w^3) \right) \right.$$

$$\left. \left(w \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} = D_B \left(\frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial C}{\partial r}\right) + \frac{D_T}{T_o} \left(\frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial C}{\partial r}\right) - Kr(C - C_o) \left(\frac{T}{T_o}\right)^n \text{Exp}\left(-\frac{E_a}{KT}\right) \right) \right| \quad (3)$$

Here, (w) denotes the axial velocity within the porous medium, while (T) and (C) represent the fluid temperature and concentration, respectively. The parameter (k) refers to the permeability of the porous matrix, and (k_f) is the thermal diffusivity of the fluid. The coefficients (D_B) and (D_m) correspond to the molecular (Brownian) diffusivity and mass diffusivity, respectively, whereas (K_T) denotes the mass diffusion ratio. The symbol (β) represents the thermal expansion coefficient, (q_R) characterizes radiation absorption, and (C_p) is the specific heat at constant pressure. Furthermore, (ρ) denotes the fluid density, (g) is the gravitational acceleration, and (ρ_{nf}) represents the effective density of the nanofluid. The effective dynamic viscosity and thermal conductivity of the nanofluid are denoted by (μ_{nf}) and (k_{nf}), respectively.

The relevant boundary conditions are:

$$w = 0, \quad T = T_w, \quad C = C_w \quad \text{at} \quad r = a \ \& \ a+s \quad (4)$$

Following Tao [28], the temperatures and concentrations at both walls are prescribed with linear axial variations, where (A) and (B) represent the imposed vertical temperature and concentration gradients. These gradients are taken to be positive for buoyancy-assisted flow and negative for buoyancy-opposed flow. Here, (T_0) and (C_0) denote the reference wall temperature and concentration at the upstream location, respectively.

The coefficient q''' is the rate of internal heat generation (>0) or absorption (<0). The internal heat generation /absorption q''' is modeled as (Emad and Abo-Eldahab et al. [28]) as

$$q''' = \left(\frac{k_f}{a^2 v}\right) (A^* (T_w - T_0) u + B^* (T - T_0)) \quad (5)$$

Where A^* and B^* are coefficients of space dependent and temperature dependent internal heat generation or absorption respectively. It is noted that the case $A^* > 0$ and $B^* > 0$, corresponds to internal heat generation and that $A^* < 0$ and $B^* < 0$, the case corresponds to internal heat absorption case. For the fully developed laminar flow in the presence of radial

magnetic field, the velocity depends only on the radial coordinate and all the other physical variables except temperature, concentration and pressure are functions of r and z , z being the vertical co-ordinate. Following Tao [31], Das et al. [32]. The temperature and concentration distributions within the fluid can thus be represented as functions of r and z .

$$T = T^*(r) + Az \quad , \quad C = C^*(r) + Bz \quad (6)$$

The properties of the nanofluids are defined as follows (see ref. [Kumar [29]]):

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{nf} &= \mu_f / (1 - \phi)^{2.5} & \alpha_{nf} &= \frac{k_{nf}}{(\rho C_p)_{nf}} & \rho_{nf} &= (1 - \phi)\rho_f + \phi\rho_s \\ (\rho C_p)_{nf} &= (1 - \phi)(\rho C_p)_f + \phi(\rho C_p)_s & (\rho\beta)_{nf} &= (1 - \phi)(\rho\beta)_f + \phi(\rho\beta)_s \\ k_{nf} &= \frac{k_f(k_s + 2k_f - 2\phi(k_f - k_s))}{(k_s + 2k_f + 2\phi(k_f - k_s))}, \sigma_{nf} = \sigma_f \left(1 + \frac{3(\sigma - 1)\phi}{\sigma + 2 - (\sigma - 1)\phi} \right), \sigma = \frac{\sigma_s}{\sigma_f} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Where the subscripts nf, f and s represent the thermo physical properties of the nanofluid, base fluid and the nanosolid particles respectively and ϕ is the solid volume fraction of the nanoparticles. The thermo physical properties of the nanofluid are given in Table 1.

The thermo physical properties of the nanofluids are given in Table 1 (See Oztop and Abu-Nada [30]).

Table – 1:

Physical properties	Base Fluid			Nanofluid
	Ethylene Glycol(Eg)	Engine oil(Eo)	Kerosene (Kr)	Ferrum oxide(Fe3O4)
C_p (j/kg K)	2430	1910	2090	670
ρ (kg m ³)	1115	884	7802430	5180
k (W/m K)	0.253	0.114	0.149	9.7
$\beta \times 10^{-5}$ 1/k)	5.7	70	99	0.50

We now define the following non-dimensional variables

$$\begin{aligned} z^* &= \frac{z}{a} \quad , \quad r^* = \frac{r}{a} \quad , \quad w^* = \left(\frac{a}{\nu}\right)w \\ p^* &= \frac{pa\delta}{\rho\nu^2}, \theta^*(r) = \frac{T^* - T_o}{P_1Aa}, \Phi = \frac{C^* - C_o}{P_1Ba} \\ s^* &= \frac{s}{a}, P_1 = \frac{dp}{dx} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Introducing these non-dimensional variables, the governing equations in the non-dimensional form are (on removing the stars)

$$\left(1 + \frac{1}{\lambda_1}\right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial w}{\partial r}\right) = A_1 A_3 + \delta A_1 \left(1 + \frac{1}{\lambda_1}\right) D^{-1} + \frac{A_6 M^2 (1 + \theta + \Phi)}{r^2} u + \delta^2 A_1 (D^{-1})^{1/2} \Delta u^2 - \delta A_1 A_4 G(\theta) = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} A_2 \left(1 + \frac{4Rd}{3}\right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial r}\right) + (A_{11}u + B_{11}\theta) + Q_1 \Phi + \left(1 + \frac{1}{\lambda_1}\right) Ec \Pr \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial r}\right)^2 \\ + A_5 Ec \Pr M^2 (1 + \alpha\theta + \beta_1 \Phi)(w^2) + A_1 \left(1 + \frac{1}{\lambda_1}\right) D^{-1} (w^2) + \Delta(w^3) = A_5 \Pr u \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial r} \right) - \gamma \Phi (1 + n\delta\theta) \text{Exp}\left(-\frac{E_1}{1 + \delta\theta}\right) = Sc u + Sc Sr \left(\frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial r} \right) \quad (11)$$

where, $\Delta = FD^{-1/2}$ (Inertia parameter or Forchheimer number), $G = \frac{\beta g P_1 A a^4}{\nu^2}$ (Grashof

number), $M^2 = \frac{\sigma \mu_e^2 H_0^2}{a \nu}$ (magnetic parameter), $D^{-1} = \frac{a^2}{k}$ (Inverse Darcy parameter),

$Pr = \frac{\mu C_p}{k_f}$ (Prandtl number), $Sc = \frac{\nu}{D_B}$ (Schmidt number), $\gamma = \frac{k_c a^2}{D_B}$ (Chemical Reaction

parameter), $Sr = \frac{D_m K_T A}{T_s B}$ (Soret number), $Q_1 = \frac{Q_1' B}{A a^2}$ (Radiation absorption parameter),

$\delta l = \theta_w - 1$, Temperature difference ratio, $E_1 = \frac{E_a}{KT_0}$ (Activation energy parameter),

$Ec = \frac{\mu_o^2}{A a^2 C_p P_1}$ (Eckert number), $A_{11} = \frac{A^*}{a}$, $B_{11} = \frac{B^*}{\nu}$ are space and temperature depending

heat source, $A_2 = (1 - \phi) + \phi \left(\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_f} \right)$, $A_3 = 1 - \phi + \phi \left(\frac{(\rho C_p)_s}{(\rho C_p)_f} \right)$, $A_4 = 1 - \phi + \phi \left(\frac{(\rho \beta)_s}{(\rho \beta)_f} \right)$,

$A_5 = \frac{k_{nf}}{k_f}$, $A_6 = \left(1 + \frac{3(\sigma - 1)}{\sigma + 2 - (\sigma - 1)\phi} \right)$, $\sigma_{nf} = \sigma_f A_6$, $\sigma = \frac{\sigma_s}{\sigma_f}$

$E_1 = \frac{E_a}{KT_0}$ (Activation energy), $\delta = \theta_w - 1$, (Temperature Difference ratio) $\theta_w = \frac{T_w}{T_0}$

The corresponding non-dimensional conditions are:

$$u = 0 \quad \theta = 0 \quad \Phi = 0 \quad \text{at } r = 1 \text{ and } 1 + s \quad (12)$$

3. Method of Solution:

Along the circular duct's radial direction, quadratic polynomial approximation functions are used for finite element analysis. The velocity, temperature, and concentration profiles are calculated and investigated for different governing factors. The variational formulation at the element level uses the Galerkin technique, and the element equations are constructed to obtain the global associated matrices for velocity, temperature, and concentration.

Choose an arbitrary element e_k and let w^k , θ^k and Φ^k be the values of w , θ and Φ in the element e_k

The error residuals are:

$$E_w^k = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\lambda_1} \right) \frac{d}{dr} \left(r \frac{dw^k}{dr} \right) - \varepsilon A_1 \left(1 + \frac{1}{\lambda_1} \right) (D^{-1}) w - \varepsilon A_1 \left(\frac{A_6 M^2 (1 + \alpha_1 w^k + \beta_1 \theta^k)}{r^2} r w^k - A_1 \varepsilon^2 (\Delta) r (w^k)^2 - A_1 A_3 \right) \quad (14)$$

$$E_\theta^k = \left(A_5 + \frac{4Rd}{3} \right) \frac{d}{dr} \left(r \frac{d\theta^k}{dr} \right) + Q_1 \Phi^k + Ec Pr \left[\left(\varepsilon A_1 \left(1 + \frac{1}{\lambda_1} \right) D^{-1} \right) (w^k)^2 + \varepsilon^2 A_1 (\Delta) (w^k)^3 + A_6 M^2 (1 + \alpha_1 \theta^k + \beta_1 \Phi^k) \right] + A_{11} w^k + B_{11} \theta^k - A_5 Pr (w^k) + (w^k)^2 \left(\frac{d^2 \theta^k}{dr^2} \right) \quad (15)$$

$$E_\Phi^k = \left(\frac{d}{dr} \left(r \frac{d\Phi^k}{dr} \right) - r Sc w^k - \gamma \Phi^k (1 + n\delta\theta^k) \text{Exp}\left(-\frac{E_1}{1 + \delta\theta^k}\right) \right) \quad (16)$$

where w^k , θ^k & Φ^k are values of w , θ & Φ in the arbitrary element e_k . These are expressed as linear combinations in terms of respective local nodal values.

$$w^k = w_1^k \psi_1^k + w_2^k \psi_2^k + w_3^k \psi_3^k, \theta^k = \theta_1^k \psi_1^k + \theta_2^k \psi_2^k + \theta_3^k \psi_3^k, \Phi^k = \Phi_1^k \psi_1^k + \Phi_2^k \psi_2^k + \Phi_3^k \psi_3^k$$

where ψ_1^k , ψ_2^k ----- etc are Lagrange's quadratic polynomials.

The weak form of the governing equations is constructed and element-level matrices are generated by integrating over each finite element, accounting for coupled velocity, temperature, and concentration fields. By enforcing boundary requirements and inter-element continuity, these local matrices form a banded and well-conditioned algebraic system with $O(N)$ computational complexity in terms of radial elements. The velocity, temperature, and concentration distributions across the domain are obtained by solving the coupled system iteratively until convergence.

The shear stress (τ) is evaluated using the formula $\tau = \left(\frac{du}{dr}\right)_{r=1,1+s}$

The rate of heat transfer (Nusselt number) is evaluated using the formula

$Nu = -(1 + Rd) \left(\frac{d\theta}{dr}\right)_{r=1,1+s}$. The rate of mass transfer (Sherwood number) is evaluated using

the formula $Sh = -\left(\frac{d\Phi}{dr}\right)_{r=1,1+s}$

4. Results and Discussion:

This study investigates the combined effects of variable viscosity, variable electrical conductivity, and Arrhenius activation energy on MHD mixed convective heat and mass transfer flow of Fe_3O_4 nanofluid confined in a vertical cylindrical annulus. Three different base fluids ethylene glycol (EG), engine oil (EO), and kerosene—are considered in the presence of a non-uniform internal heat source. The nonlinear, coupled governing equations are solved numerically using the finite element method (FEM) with quadratic interpolation functions.

The variations of axial velocity w , temperature θ , and nanoparticle concentration Φ for different parameters are illustrated in Figs. 2–17.

Figs. 2a–2c illustrate the influence of the Grashof number G . An increase in G leads to a reduction in velocity, temperature, and nanoparticle concentration across all base fluids. Among the three, EG-based Fe_3O_4 nanofluid exhibits the highest velocity and temperature profiles, whereas EO-based nanofluid shows comparatively higher nanoparticle concentration. Figs. 3a–3c show that increasing the magnetic parameter M suppresses velocity and concentration due to the enhanced Lorentz force, while temperature increases because of Joule heating. EG-based nanofluid consistently maintains higher velocity and temperature, whereas EO-based nanofluid exhibits stronger concentration levels.

As depicted in Figs. 4 -5, increasing the porous permeability parameter k reduces velocity, temperature, and concentration throughout the annulus due to increased resistance offered by the porous matrix. The Forchheimer (inertia) parameter Δ reduces velocity by thinning the momentum, thermal, and solutal boundary layers.

Thermal radiation (Rd) enhances velocity and nanoparticle concentration but reduces temperature (Figs. 6a–6c), indicating radiation-induced energy redistribution within the flow field.

An increase in the Eckert number Ec reduces velocity and concentration while enhancing temperature (Figs. 7a–7c), reflecting the conversion of kinetic energy into internal energy. Higher nanoparticle volume fraction ϕ enhances velocity, temperature, and concentration in all base fluids (Figs. 8a–8c) due to improved thermal conductivity and intensified Brownian motion.

The space-dependent heat source parameter A_{11} increases concentration while decreasing

temperature (Figs. 9a–9b), whereas the temperature-dependent heat source parameter B_{11} concentration but enhances temperature (Figs. 10a–10b). An increase in the Schmidt number Sc increases the concentration profile (Fig.11), owing to reduced molecular diffusivity.

Thermo-diffusion (Sr) enhances concentration (Fig. 12), whereas a degenerating chemical reaction (γ) leads to a reduction in temperature and concentration profiles (Figs. 13a–13b). Radiation absorption parameter Q_1 increases temperature (Fig. 14). An increase in activation energy E_1 enhances temperature and nanoparticle concentration (Figs. 15a–15b), as higher activation energy weakens the chemical reaction rate, allowing thermal energy and species accumulation. The Casson parameter λ_1 suppresses velocity while thickening thermal and solutal boundary layers (Figs. 16a–16c). EG-based nanofluid maintains higher velocity, while EO-based nanofluid exhibits lower temperature profiles. An increase in the Prandtl number Pr decreases velocity and concentration and enhances temperature due to reduced thermal diffusivity (Figs. 17a–17c).

Across all parametric variations, EG-based Fe_3O_4 nanofluid consistently exhibits the highest velocity and temperature profiles, while EO-based Fe_3O_4 nanofluid shows relatively higher nanoparticle concentration. This confirms that base-fluid thermophysical properties play a dominant role in governing MHD heat and mass transfer characteristics in cylindrical annular nanofluid flows.

Fig.2: Variation of [a] Velocity (w), [b] Temperature(θ), [c] Nanoconcentration(Φ) with G $M=0.5, K=0.2, B=0.25, Rd=0.5, Ec=0.1, \phi=0.05, A_{11}=0.1, B_{11}=0.1, Sc=0.24, Sr=0.25, \gamma=0.5, Q_1=0.25, \Delta=0.1, E_1=0.1, \delta=0.1, n=0.2, \alpha=0.2, \beta_1=0.2, De_1=0.1, De_2=0.1, Pr=0.71, \lambda_1=0.1$

Fig.3a-3c: Impact of M on w , θ and Φ

Fig.4: Impact of K on w

Fig.5: Impact of K on θ

Fig.6: Impact of Rd on w , θ and Φ

Fig.7a-7c: Impact of Ec on w , θ and Φ

Fig.8a-8c: Impact of ϕ on w , θ and Φ

Fig.9a-9b: Impact of A_{11} on θ and Φ

Fig.10a-10b: Impact of B_{11} on θ and Φ

Fig.12: Impact of Sr on Φ

Fig.11: Impact of Sc on w, θ and Φ

Fig.13a-13b: Impact of γ on θ and Φ

Fig.14: Impact of Q1 on θ

Fig.15a-15b: Impact of $E1$ on θ and Φ

Fig. 16a-16c: Impact of λ_1 on w , θ and Φ

Fig. 17a-17c: Impact of Pr on w , θ and Φ

5. Validation of the Results:

Comparison of Skin friction(τ), Nusselt number (Nu) and Sherwood number (Sh)at $r=1$ & 2 (Fe_3O_4/Eg) Cylindrical annulus. In the case of Newtonian fluid ($\lambda_1=0$) and Activation energy($E1=\delta=0$) the results are in good agreement with Shamshuddin et. al. [26]. A direct comparison of Table 3 (inner wall, $r = 1$) and Table 4 (outer wall, $r = 2$) reveals a clear wall-dependent transport behavior in the cylindrical annulus. At the inner wall ($r = 1$), the magnitudes of the skin friction coefficient are generally higher, while the Nusselt and Sherwood numbers are comparatively lower, indicating stronger shear effects but weaker heat and mass transfer due to near-wall resistance and confinement. In contrast, at the outer wall ($r = 2$), heat and mass transfer rates (Nu and Sh) are consistently enhanced, reflecting the dominance of buoyancy driven convection and reduced thermal resistance away from the inner surface. For most governing parameters (such as G , Rd , Φ , Sr , $E1$), variations produce opposite or amplified trends at ($r = 2$) compared to ($r = 1$), while magnetic field, viscous dissipation, and Forchheimer resistance suppress transport at both walls. Across both tables, ethylene glycol-based Fe_3O_4 nanofluid exhibits superior heat transfer, whereas engine oil-based Fe_3O_4 nanofluid shows stronger mass transfer, with kerosene-based nanofluid yielding the lowest transport rates. Overall, the comparison confirms that outer-wall transport is more convection-dominated, whereas inner-wall transport is shear-dominated, highlighting the critical role of radial position in annular nanofluid heat and mass transfer.

Table 3: In the case of Newtonian fluid ($\lambda_1=0$) and Activation energy($E1=\delta=0$) the results are in good agreement with Shamshuddin et. al.[45]:

Rd	Pr	Sr	B1	Q1	ϕ	γ	Shamshuddin et. al [26]			Present Outcomes		
							τ (1)	Nu (1)	Sh (1)	Sh (1)	Nu (2)	Sh (2)
0.5	0.71	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.02	0.05	-	0.1378	0.1316	-	0.1378	0.1316
							0.7320	81	33	0.7320	82	33
							72			62		
1.0							-	0.0973	0.1039	-	0.0973	0.1039
							0.7526	78	20	0.7526	12	20
							42			82		
1.5							-	0.0657	0.0646	-	0.0657	0.0646
							0.7695	88	78	0.7695	91	78
							43			42		
	1.71						-	0.0339	0.0605	-	0.0339	0.0605
							0.7535	62	15	0.7535	64	16
							34			39		

Rd	Pr	Sr	B1	Q1	ϕ	γ	Shamshuddin et. al [26]			Present Outcomes		
							τ (1)	Nu (1)	Sh (1)	Sh (1)	Nu (2)	Sh (2)
	5.00						- 0.7496 71	0.3145 67	0.2515 72	- 0.7496 83	0.3145 66	0.2515 72
		1.0					- 0.7514 52	0.1819 73	0.1098 60	- 0.7514 64	0.1819 71	0.1098 60
		1.5					- 0.7514 12	0.1848 10	0.1953 88	- 0.7514 71	0.1848 11	0.1953 88
			1.0				- 0.7513 36	0.1901 94	0.1653 91	- 0.7513 33	0.1902 03	0.1653 91
			1.5				- 0.7511 33	0.2045 82	0.1774 25	- 0.7511 35	0.2045 83	0.1774 25
				1.0			- 0.7413 96	0.1859 69	0.1652 68	- 0.7414 01	0.1859 71	0.1652 68
				1.5			- 0.7411 75	0.2015 81	0.1752 15	- 0.7411 76	0.2015 88	0.1752 15
					0.03		- 0.7254 32	0.1312 76	0.1289 76	- 0.7254 22	0.1312 77	0.1289 77
					0.05		- 0.7104 57	0.1278 66	0.1204 56	- 0.7104 58	0.1278 60	0.1204 57

Rd	Pr	Sr	B1	Q1	ϕ	γ	Shamshuddin et al [45] results			Present Outcomes		
							τ (2)	Nu(2)	Sh(2)	Sh(1)	Nu(2)	Sh(2)
0.5	0.71	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.05	0.05	0.6014 45	- 0.0995 12	- 0.0951 16	0.6014 38	- 0.0995 10	- 0.0951 17
1.0							0.6018 49	- 0.0702 93	- 0.0751 06	0.6018 44	- 0.0702 91	- 0.0751 01
1.5							0.6022 34	- 0.0244 89	- 0.0606 78	0.6022 31	- 0.0244 91	- 0.0606 79
	1.71						0.6024 82	- 0.0244 89	- 0.0437 33	0.6024 80	- 0.0244 89	- 0.0437 33
	5.00						0.5996 96	- 0.2259 9	- 0.1817 41	0.5996 81	- 0.2259 91	- 0.1817 44

Rd	Pr	Sr	B1	Q1	φ	γ	Shamshuddin et al [45] results			Present Outcomes		
							τ(2)	Nu(2)	Sh(2)	Sh(1)	Nu(2)	Sh(2)
		1.0					0.601005	-0.131324	-0.079384	0.601002	-0.131324	-0.079387
		1.5					0.6009775	-0.133333	-0.141136	0.600970	-0.133332	-0.141138
			1.0				0.600923	-0.137323	0.120887	0.600921	-0.137323	0.120885
			1.5				0.600779	-0.147315	0.127854	0.600788	-0.147321	0.127850
				1.0			0.600965	-0.134528	0.118842	0.600966	-0.134521	0.118842
				1.5			-0.600809	-0.146208	0.126404	0.600809	-0.146209	0.126403
					0.10		0.599567	-0.094564	-0.09345	0.599567	-0.094566	-0.093456
					0.15		0.5896788	-0.091234	-0.091234	0.589679	-0.091233	-0.091239

Table 3: Skin friction (τ), Nusselt and Sherwood number (Nu, Sh) at r=1:

Parameters		Fe3o4-Eg nanofluid			Fe3o4-Eo-nanofluid			Fe3o4-kerosene nanofluid		
		τ(1)	Nu (1)	Sh (1)	τ (1)	Nu (1)	Sh (1)	τ (1)	Nu (1)	Sh (1)
G	2	-0.50146	-0.0129088	-0.0061089	-0.50158	-0.00585703	-0.0076458	-0.50022	-0.00761304	-0.0072431
	4	-0.50026	-0.012847	-0.0060973	-0.49954	-0.00582062	-0.0076210	-0.49783	-0.00754082	-0.00720917
M	0.5	-0.50026	-0.012847	-0.0060977	-0.49954	-0.00582062	-0.0076201	-0.49783	-0.00754082	-0.0072097
	1.0	-0.49974	-0.0146322	-0.0056967	-0.49882	-0.00662386	-0.0074305	-0.49606	-0.00856739	-0.0069623
K	0.2	-0.50026	-0.012847	-0.0060973	-0.49954	-0.00582062	-0.0076211	-0.49783	-0.00754082	-0.0072097
	0.4	-0.49592	-0.0126209	-0.0060545	-0.49518	-0.00571848	-0.0075529	-0.49354	-0.00740938	-0.0071468

	0.50	-0.49783	-0.0128523	-0.0060983	-0.49950	-0.0058217	-0.0076217	-0.49783	-0.00754262	-0.00721
Rd	0.5	-0.49908	-0.012786	-0.0060886	-0.49796	-0.00578474	-0.0075966	-0.49783	-0.00754082	-0.0072097
	1.5	-0.501798	-0.00464813	-0.00792566	-0.501455	-0.00218715	-0.00845896	-0.500827	-0.00281921	-0.00830735
Ec	0.1	-0.500266	-0.012847	-0.00609737	-0.499504	-0.00582062	-0.00762101	-0.497834	-0.00754082	-0.00720917
	0.2	-0.499005	-0.0212894	-0.00422354	-0.497872	-0.00962764	-0.00675267	-0.49567	-0.0124229	-0.00608
A11	0.1	-0.500266	-0.012847	-0.00609737	-0.499504	-0.00582062	-0.00762101	-0.497834	-0.00754082	-0.00762101
	0.2	-0.500302	-0.0127159	-0.00612678	-0.499551	-0.00576143	-0.00763498	-0.497905	-0.00746469	-0.00763498
B11	0.1	-0.500266	-0.012847	-0.00609737	-0.499504	-0.00582062	-0.00762101	-0.497834	-0.00754082	-0.00720917
	0.3	-0.500265	-0.0128507	-0.00609655	-0.499504	-0.00582137	-0.00762083	-0.497833	-0.00754208	-0.00720887
φ	0.05	-0.499082	-0.012786	-0.0125267	-0.497969	-0.00578474	-0.00567609	-0.497834	-0.00754082	-0.00739697
	0.1	-0.501344	-0.0129295	-0.0126889	-0.499261	-0.00582764	-0.00572856	-0.496949	-0.00753066	-0.00740105
λ1		-0.217484	1.00882	-0.073225	-0.145923	-1.007424	-0.07362	0.00170611	-1.00552	-0.073842
		-0.353349	1.00894	-0.0729257	-0.164104	-1.007444	-0.07195	0.005005	-1.00603	-0.06949
Sc	0.24	-----	-0.012847	-0.00609737	-----	-0.00582062	-0.00762101	-----	-0.00754082	-0.00720917
	0.66	---	-0.0128688	-0.0312402	---	-0.005832	-0.0395553	---	-0.00755495	-0.0373113
Sr	0.25	-----	-0.012847	-0.00609737	-----	-0.00582062	-0.00762101	-----	-0.00754082	-0.00720917

	0.50	----- ---	- 0.0128 459	- 0.0038 6102	----- ----	- 0.0058 2038	- 0.0066 0677	----- --	- 0.0075 4043	- 0.0058 952
γ	0.5	----- -	- 0.0128 47	- 0.0060 9737	----- ---	- 0.0058 2062	- 0.0076 2101	----- ---	- 0.0075 4082	- 0.0072 0917
	1.0		- 0.0128 47	- 0.0059 8684	---	- 0.0058 2058	- 0.0075 0241	---	- 0.0075 077	- 0.0070 9294
Δ	□	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	□	0.500 266	0.0128 47	0.0060 9737	0.499 504	0.0058 2062	0.0076 2101	0.4978 34	0.0075 4082	0.0072 0917
	□	0.492 9	0.0124 663	0.0060 2464	0.491 464	0.0056 3236	0.0074 9185	0.4882 8	0.0072 5086	0.0070 7053
Q1	0.25	- 0.500 266	- 0.0128 47	- 0.0060 9737	- 0.499 504	- 0.0058 2062	- 0.0076 2101	- 0.4978 34	- 0.0075 4082	- 0.0072 0917
	0.50	- 0.500 265	- 0.0128 518	- 0.0060 963	- 0.499 502	- 0.0058 2309	- 0.0076 2042	- 0.4978 31	- 0.0075 4389	- 0.0072 0843
E1	0.1	- 0.500 266	- 0.0128 47	- 0.0060 9737	- 0.499 504	- 0.0058 2062	- 0.0076 2101	- 0.4978 34	- 0.0075 4081	- 0.0071 8566
	0.2	- 0.500 266	- 0.0128 471	- 0.0061 2521	- 0.499 504	- 0.0058 2062	- 0.0076 3633	- 0.4978 34	- 0.0075 4084	- 0.0072 3841
δ	0.1	- 0.500 266	- 0.0128 47	- 0.0060 9737	- 0.499 504	- 0.0058 2062	- 0.0076 2101	- 0.4978 34	- 0.0075 4081	- 0.0071 8566
	0.2	- 0.500 266	- 0.0128 47	- 0.0060 9736	- 0.499 504	- 0.0058 2061	- 0.0076	- 0.4978 34	- 0.0075 4082	- 0.0072 0916
n	0.2	- 0.500 266	- 0.0128 47	- 0.0060 9737	- 0.500 266	- 0.0058 2062	- 0.0076 2101	- 0.4995 04	- 0.0075 4082	- 0.0072 0917
	0.4	- 0.497 833	- 0.0128 523	- 0.0060 9835	- 0.499 504	- 0.0058 217	- 0.0076 2173	- 0.4978 34	- 0.0075 4262	- 0.0072 1
	0.3	- 0.500 268	- 0.0128 471	- 0.0060 9739	- 0.499 506	- 0.0058 2066	- 0.0076 031	- 0.4978 36	- 0.0075 4088	- 0.0072 0919
Pr	0.71	- 0.502 439	- 0.0012 4301	- 0.0086 862	- 0.502 332	- 0.0005 65123	- 0.0088 3342	- 0.5021 56	- 0.0007 36405	- 0.0087 924
	1.71	- 0.500 266	- 0.0128 47	- 0.0060 9737	- 0.499 504	- 0.0058 2062	- 0.0076 2101	- 0.4973 4	- 0.0075 4082	- 0.0072 0917

Table 4: Skin friction (τ), Nusselt and Sherwood number (Nu,Sh) at $r=2$:

param eters	Fe3o4-Eg nanofluid			Fe3o4-Eo-nanofluid			Fe3o4-kerosene nanofluid		
	$\tau(2)$	Nu (2)	Sh(2)	$\tau(2)$	Nu (2)	Sh(2)	$\tau(2)$	Nu(2)	Sh(2)
G	0.486 358	0.0126 466	0.0060 5054	0.486 043	0.0057 4683	0.0075 4512	0.485 251	0.0074 6762	0.0071 5297
	0.485 208	0.0125 863	0.0060 3897	0.484 548	0.0057 112	0.0075 2075	0.482 972	0.0073 9697	0.0071 1938
M	0.485 208	0.0125 863	0.0060 3897	0.484 548	0.0057 112	0.0075 2075	0.482 972	0.0073 9697	0.0071 1938
	0.484 706	0.0143 491	0.0056 4699	0.483 896	0.0065 0625	0.0073 3392	0.481 984	0.0084 1268	0.0068 7745
K	- 0.012 845	- 0.0060 973	0.0060 3897	- 0.005 820	- 0.0076 2101	0.0075 2075	- 0.754 082	- 0.0072 0917	0.0071 1938
	- 0.012 625	- 0.0060 544	0.0059 9611	- 0.005 718	- 0.0075 5129	0.0074 5193	- 0.740 938	- 0.0071 4682	0.0070 5773
	0.485 204	0.0125 914	0.0060 3994	0.484 546	0.0057 1224	0.0075 2145	0.482 969	0.0073 9869	0.0071 2021
Rd	0.484 069	0.0125 267	0.0060 2748	0.483 074	0.0056 7609	0.0074 9663	0.482 972	0.0073 9697	0.0071 1938
	0.486 683	0.0045 61	0.0078 179	0.486 426	0.0021 4752	0.0083 3798	0.485 854	0.0027 6779	0.0081 9007
Ec	0.485 208	0.0125 863	0.0060 3897	0.484 548	0.0057 112	0.0075 2075	0.482 972	0.0073 9697	0.0071 1938
	0.483 993	0.0208 191	0.0042 2035	0.482 976	0.0094 2837	0.0066 7664	0.480 597	0.0121 6267	0.0060 3009
A11	0.485 208	0.0125 863	0.0060 3897	0.484 548	0.0057 112	0.0075 2075	0.482 972	0.0073 9697	0.0071 1938
	0.485 243	0.0124 565	0.0060 6784	0.484 593	0.0056 5245	0.0075 3449	0.483 041	0.0073 2142	0.0071 3728
B11	0.485 208	0.0125 863	0.0060 3897	0.484 548	0.0057 112	0.0075 2075	0.482 972	0.0073 9697	0.0071 1938
	0.485 207	0.0125 896	0.0060 3816	0.484 547	0.0057 1194	0.0075 2057	0.482 971	0.0073 9889	0.0071 1909
ϕ	0.484 069	0.0125 267	0.0060 2748	0.483 076	0.0056 7609	0.0074 9663	0.482 972	0.0073 9697	0.0071 1938
	0.487 634	0.0126 889	0.0060 5669	0.485 778	0.0057 2856	0.0075 3062	0.483 605	0.0074 0105	0.0071 1922
λ_1	- 0.024 54	0.9890 7	0.0060 2657	0.035 14	- 0.9944 9	0.0058 799	0.424 33	- 0.9956 99	0.0057 869
	- 0.043 22	0.9888 5	0.0060 2567	0.042 87	- 0.9944 5	0.0059 876	0.478 65	- 0.9948 38	0.0058 123

Sc	0.484 068 0.478 965	0.0125 863	0.0060 3897	0.476 068	0.0057 112	0.0075 2075	0.465 068	0.0073 9697	0.0071 1938
		12607 7456	0.0295 784	0.470 865	0.0057 2243	0.0374 4745	0.460 965	0.0074 1898	0.0353 218
Sr	0.484 068 0.479 965	0.0125 863	0.0060 3897	0.473 068	0.0057 112	0.0075 2075	0.465 068	0.0073 9697	0.0071 1938
		0.0125 852	0.0038 6163	0.465 78	0.0057 1097	0.0065 3173	0.458 799	0.0073 9657	0.0058 878
γ^{\wedge}	0.484 068 0.498 965	0.0125 863	0.0060 3897	0.465 4068	0.0057 112	0.0075 2075	0.459 968	0.0073 9697	0.0071 1938
		0.0125 862	0.0059 2975	0.477 6965	0.0057 1116	0.0074 0356	0.465 4765	0.0073 9692	0.0070 0454
Δ	0.485 208	0.0125 863	0.0060 3897	0.484 548	0.0057 112	0.0075 2075	0.482 972	0.0073 9697	0.0071 1938
	0.478 143	0.0122 147	0.0059 6635	0.476 831	0.0055 2716	0.0073 9323	0.473 797	0.0071 1354	0.0069 8225
Q1	0.485 208	0.0125 863	0.0060 3897	0.484 548	0.0057 112	0.0075 2075	0.482 972	0.0073 9697	0.0071 1938
	0.485 207	0.0125 915	0.0060 3792	0.484 546	0.0057 1365	0.0075 2017	0.482 978	0.0074 0002	0.0071 1866
E1	0.485 208	0.0125 863	0.0060 3897	0.484 548	0.0057 112	0.0075 2075	0.482 972	0.0073 9696	0.0070 9619
	0.485 208	0.0125 863	0.0060 6648	0.484 548	0.0057 112	0.0075 3859	0.482 972	0.0073 9698	0.0071 4828
δ	0.485 208	0.0125 863	0.0060 3897	0.484 548	0.0057 112	0.0075 2075	0.482 972	0.0073 9696	0.0070 9619
	0.485 208	0.0125 8637	0.0060 3896	0.484 548	0.0057 1119	0.0075 0304	0.482 972	0.0073 9692	0.0071 1938
n	0.485 208	0.0125 863	0.0060 3897	0.484 548	0.0057 112	0.0075 2075	0.482 972	0.0073 9697	0.0071 1938
	0.485 204	0.0125 914	0.0060 3994	0.484 546	0.0057 1224	0.0075 2145	0.482 969	0.0073 9869	0.0071 2021
	0.485 215	0.0125 864	0.0060 3899	0.484 549	0.0057 1124	0.0075 0308	0.482 974	0.0073 9702	0.0071 1941
Pr	0.487 301	0.0012 244	0.0085 5972	0.487 278	0.0005 5478	0.0087 0357	0.487 133	0.0007 2294	0.0086 6363
	0.485 208	0.0125 863	0.0060 3897	0.484 548	0.0057 112	0.0075 2075	0.482 972	0.0073 9697	0.0071 1938

6. Conclusions

- The applied magnetic field significantly suppresses axial velocity and nanoparticle concentration due to Lorentz force effects, while enhancing temperature as a result of Joule heating.
- Darcy–Forchheimer porous medium resistance strongly reduces flow velocity and weakens thermal and solutal transport by increasing inertial and drag forces within the annular region.

- Viscous dissipation elevates temperature while reducing velocity and concentration, confirming the conversion of kinetic energy into internal energy in high-shear regimes.
- Increasing Arrhenius activation energy enhances temperature and nanoparticle concentration by weakening chemical reaction rates, leading to thicker thermal and concentration boundary layers.
- A clear wall-dependent behavior is observed: inner-wall transport is shear-dominated with higher skin friction, while outer-wall transport is convection-dominated with enhanced heat and mass transfer rates.
- Among the base fluids considered, ethylene glycol-based Fe_3O_4 nanofluid provides the best overall thermal performance, whereas engine oil-based nanofluid exhibits stronger mass transfer, highlighting the importance of base-fluid selection for applications in heat exchangers, MHD cooling systems, chemical reactors, geothermal devices, and energy conversion systems involving porous annular geometries.

Future work:

Future investigations may extend the present model by incorporating nanoparticle shape effects, temperature-dependent thermophysical properties, and hybrid or ternary nanofluids to further enhance transport performance. The inclusion of unsteady flow conditions, Hall and ion-slip currents, slip boundary conditions, and experimental validation would provide deeper insight into practical applications. Additionally, optimization studies and entropy generation analysis could be explored to assess the thermodynamic efficiency of annular MHD nanofluid systems under realistic operating conditions.

Author Contributions

P. Chandrakala conceived the study, developed the mathematical model, performed the numerical analysis, and prepared the original manuscript.

G. Ven Gopala Krishna contributed to model formulation, numerical implementation, and result interpretation.

T. Koteswara Rao assisted with literature review, validation, and manuscript revision. Srijana Sharma contributed to data analysis, figure interpretation, and final proofreading. All authors reviewed and approved the final manuscript.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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This study does not involve human participants or animals. Ethical approval is not applicable.

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All authors have read and approved the manuscript and consent to its publication.

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No data were generated or analyzed during the current study.

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